

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A533

5 April 1997

OXICOA

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 533

DATE: 05 104 197

Take off : 08 10

Landing : 15 10

Aircraft Scientist : KATE, RICHER

Flight Leader : PERCIVAL

Others : DEWEY, KENT,
TIDDEMAN, BANDY,
BAUGWITTE, GIDDINAS,
MILLS, PENNETT,
LAW, PIPHERING,
PURSE, GREEN,
LANGRIDGE, BOYD.

Captain : SQN LDR O'BRIEN

Co-pilot : FLT LT THORNHILL

Navigator : FLT LT CANNING

Engineer : SGT LENNARDS

Loadmaster : M. ENG QUICK

FLY LT PURSE

FLY LT MORRIS

Trials Instructions TACIA :

Operating area : PRESTWICK TO SANTA MARIA, AZORES.

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A533, 5th April, 1997
 ACSOE
 Prestwick to Santa Maria.

Start time	End time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
080845					Take off from Prestwick
081412	081917	R1	4000'	280°	Instrument warm up run
082330	082503	R2	FL085	300°	Cloud Free Run
083649	085854	R3	FL160	290°	
090826	092800	P1	FL160- 900ft	270°	1000fpm, 500fpm from 8000'
092818	093717	R4	1000'	270°	
093717	094444	P2.1	1000' - FL050	270°	500fpm
094444	095152	R5	FL050	270°	
095152	095650	P2.2	FL050- FL100	270°	1000fpm
095650	100348	R6.1	FL100	270°	
100348	101012	R6.2	FL100	270°	
101012	101513	P2.3	FL100- FL150	265°	1000fpm
101513	102012	R7	FL150	265°	
102012	102627	P2.4	FL150- FL200	220°	1000fpm
102627	104337	R8	FL200	225°	Accelerate to 220kts
132441	134433	R9	FL200	220°	230kts IAS
134523	135006	P3.1	FL200- FL150	225°	1000fpm 180kts IAS.
135006	135646	R10	FL150	225°	
135646	140135	P3.2	FL150- FL100	230°	1000fpm
140135	140851	R11	FL100	225°	
140851	141259	P3.3	FL100- 6000'	230°	1000fpm
141259	143231	R12	6000'	235°	
143231	143519	P3.4	6000' - 3500'	180°	1000fpm
143519	144055	R13	3500'	180°	
144055	144717	P3.5	3500' - 50 ft	180°	500fpm
144822	145804	R14	100'	110°	Artifact run.
150730					Land at Santa Maria. 36°58.30'N 025°09.85'W

A533 05-APR-97 08:08:45-15:07:30GMT

A533 05-APR-97 Height time series

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACSOE

Date: 5/4/97

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Flight No: A533

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
..	19	P1c	900	P				
9:28:19	20	R4	1000	P	259	55.72 -10.55	in cloud ^{8. Pentact.} decision made not to descend descend to 50' because of cloud	
9:37:24	21	R4/P2.1	1000	P	259	55.02 -11.18	in cloud.	
9:42:45			3800	P			precipitation - window.	
9:44:48	22	P2.1 R5	050	F	262	55.72 -11.70	out of cloud 8/8 sc below alt to ci above.	
9:51:52	23	R5 P2.2	050	F	258	55.62 -12.25	Precip on window solid cloud above and below in a thick veil of cloud.	
9:56:21	.					55.56 -12.54	cloud top 9100 FLO91	
9:56:51	24	P2.2 R6.1	100	F	260	55.55 -12.61	Zero runs started.	
10:03:46	25	R6.1 R6.2	100	F	255	55.42 -12.23	IN cloud.	
10:10:13	26	R6.4 P2.3	100	F	249	55.30 -13.72	in cloud in and out of cloud as climb.	
10:15:14	27	P2.3 R7	150	F	255	55.20 -14.13	in cloud... $\frac{3}{4}$ with bright flashes so we must be near the top.	
10:17:38						55.15 -14.38	out of cloud * cloud top slipping away.	
10:20:15	28	R7 P2.4	150	F	251	55.11 -14.50	small wisps of an above 8/8 sc below NO ci above.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACSOE

Date: 5/14/77

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Flight No: A533

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
10:26:29	29	2.4/R8	200	F	209	54.99	-15.02	clear above 7/8 sc below. Several layers vis Below.
10:43:30	30	R8e	200	F	211	53.79	-15.81	end of run 5/8 sc below, clear above.
13:24:40	31	R9	200	F	188	41.44	-22.56	Start of NOXY Calibration Run clear above
								Someci visible in the distance solid sc below.
13:38:09		R9	200	F	195	40.36	-22.80	clear above solid sc. Below.
13:44:33	32	R9e	200	F	215	39.05	-23.25	end of High Speed runs.
13:45:25	33	P3.1	200	F	216	39.79	-23.31	3/8 sc below some gaps.
13:50:06	34	P3.1 R10	150	F	217	37.56	-23.55	Some streets visible in the SC below.
13:56:47	35	R10 P3.2	150	F	216	39.24	-23.07	7/8 sc below. clear above.
14:01:35	36	P3.2 R11	100	F	218	37.02	-24.08	8/8 sc below clear above.
14:08:50	37	P3.3	100	F	213	38.66	-24.45	hazy ahead 8/8 sc below.
14:13:00	38	P3.3 R12	6000	P	213	38.47	-24.63	sc below clear above 20 minute run east 15 mi long cal for Perov & Hetero
14:14:00	39		6000	P	219	38.33	-24.00	8/8 sc below sea visible through gaps.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: ACSOE

Date: 5/14/97

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Flight No: A533

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height		INS	Omega		Other Info. (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			Pres/Rad	FL		Latitude	Longitude	
14:24:44		R 12	6000	P	219	37.99	-25.21	mountains of Punta del Encarda visible through clouds.
14:32:32	40	R12/P3.4	6000	P	160	37.67	-25.59	clear air sea calm no white caps
13:35:22		R13	3500	P	168	37.51	-25.55	Sc ahead clear above & below no white caps visible.
14:40:56	42	R13/P3.4	3500	P	168	37.21	-25.83	No ci solid sc. 3000 cloud top. 2000ft cloud base
14:44:45			1300	P	157	37.06	-25.49	hazy some white caps visible.
14:45:17	43	P 3.4e	50	R	159	36.96	-25.46	1016 sea state 4
14:48:23	45	R14	100	R	93	36.96	-25.38	hazy under sc.
14:53:25	46	R14e	100	R	102	36.79	-24.95	" "
End of Science.								

OXICOA: Air Mass Characterization Transit

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

To observe the transition in atmospheric chemical composition across the polar front. The data will be added to a systematically collected air mass data base. The data base will be used to determine the oxidising capacity and the budget of tropospheric oxidants in marine air at mid latitudes in the northern hemisphere..

LOCATION: North Atlantic Ocean

WEATHER: Cloud Free

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Prestwick and transit to sampling area at convenient altitude.
 - [1.1] Hold climb at ~~3000~~⁴ ft for wet chemistry check.
 - [1.2] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed 180 kts.) for NO_x Calibration.
- [2] Stepped profile ascent from 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) to approx. FL200 — 500ft/min below approx. FL70, 1000ft/min above.
 - [2.1] Interrupt profile to fill bottles and/or bags (= 8 min) at:

1 bag + 1 bottle at each level.

100', 3000' ~~FL 60~~, FL 100, FL 150, FL 200.
- [3] Transit to Santa Maria ATC (or until good radio contact established with Santa Maria) at ~~FL 150 and 180 kts.~~ ^{FL 200} 1 bag every 15 min.
- [4] Stepped profile descent from approx. FL200 to 50ft (or minimum safe altitude) — 1000ft/min until approx. FL70 then 500ft/min.
 - [4.1] Interrupt profile to fill bottles and/or bags (= 8 min) at:

1 bag + 1 bottle at each level

FL 200, FL 150, FL 100, FL 70, 3000', 100'.
- [5] Transit to Santa Maria as convenient.
 - [5.1] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed 180 kts) for NO_x Calibration.

10 minutes — before final approach

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure and temperature to be kept constant on level runs.

MISSION SCIENTIST'S LOG Project: OXICA Date: 5/4/97

21L

Mission Scientist: S. Penkett
K. Lall

Flight No: A533 Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run No.	Notes:	
08:14:12	R1	05?	Soppbr 03 05 - 0.2 ppbv H ₂ O ₂
	R2	085	Aborted for Navy
	P3	085-15	Generally good H ₂ O ₂ :O ₃
	R3	016	correlation in "profile" (from ground)
		→ 020?	But XY plot flat (no H ₂ O ₂ lag)
			Daily constant org. peroxide ~ 0.1 ppbv.
			O ₃ inc [↑] at cut FL by Spp br.
			Top of profile O ₃ - 58.94 ppbv
09:08:26	P1	FL160 → FL10	[Sun at 10. 30 ⁵⁰ 100 150 200]
			Low O ₃ layer at 3000 4km
	R4		Straight down - no steps/Guttles
09:28:03	P2	FL10 (7-8 min)	Very low H ₂ O ₂ in M3 (0.1 ppbv)
			OK in: strat strat to the uniform ^{REC.}
09:37:26	P2-1	FL10 → FL50	HCHO - difficult to see - offset
			est. 500-600 pptv range
09:44:44	R5	FL50	higher pp H ₂ O ₂ above
09:51:52	P2-2	FL50 → FL100	low profile slightly warmer
			(land top 8000ft)
09:56:50	R6-1	FL100	zeroing
10:03:48	6-2		→ still uniform - org peroxide ~ 0.1 ppbv
10:10:12	P3-1	FL100 → FL150	Continuing profile, slightly less H ₂ O ₂
10:15:13	R7	FL150	(φ=58°)
10:20:12	P4-2-4	FL150 → FL200	Next leg (turning south)
			spike in O ₃ at 6000m (20,000ft)
	R8	FL200	printed O ₃ /H ₂ O ₂ at 10:31:14
			hooking at O ₃ : H ₂ O ₂ 10:30 → 10:40
			there was a layer 5-thin (calc 2) where
			there is anti-correlation
			N ₂ O ₂ ~ 0.2 → 400 ppbv - everything max
			NO ₂ → 100-200 ppbv.
11:49			feature in NO ₂ , N ₂ O ₂ , O ₃ , H ₂ O ₂
			- all inc [↑] followed by smaller

S.F. 1 ppbv - Navy
250 NO₂
150. NO

MISSION SCIENTIST'S LOG Project: OXICOA Date: 5/14/1977

Mission Scientist: S. Penhelt
K. Lavi

Flight No: A533 Page 2 of 2

GMT	Run No.	FL 150, 100, 60, 30, 10	Notes:
13:45:31	P3-1	FL200 →	41°N, 24°W (approx.) O3 levels at 50-60 ppbv.
13:50:06	R10		large inc in H ₂ O ₂
	P3-2		
	R11	FL 100 ¹⁰⁰	H ₂ O ₂ starting to inc around 12000 ft
	P3-3		
14:09	R12	FL 100 ⁶⁰	O3 inc, NOy ↓ with altitude H ₂ O ₂ correlating with O3 mod H ₂ O ₂ diverging by more than further north (now 2.5 ppbv). Near H ₂ O ₂ up to 1.5 ppbv (3x > than mod H ₂ O ₂ up to 4.5 b.
14:13:19	P3-4	FL60 → FL3	Now O3 is uniform around 50 ppbv. one layer (14:35) → ⁶⁰⁰ 600 ppbv NOy (approx)
	R13	FL35	70 ppbv O ₃ 400 ppbv NO ₂ (approx conv!)
14:1	P3-5	FL35-FL10	
14:48:22	R14	FL100	
14:58:04	finish		

55%

5200 ft

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 533

Date: 05.04.97

A/S Name: AKAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for5.....

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of ProjectACSOE.....

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long?10 YRS.....

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data **TEMPORARILY** until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A 5 33 Date: 0504 97 User: KATE / MERC
Interactive by: D PERCIVAL
Date: 15 04 97

Renav

Kalman Filtering Applied

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile (Whole flight / Other

$$a = - 0.5048 E^{01}$$

$$b = + 0.4123 E^{-2}$$

$$c = + 0.1561 E^{-6}$$

ok

LWC

ok

Heimann / Barnes

ok

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A533

Date: 0504 97

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0641	REF +	5	0567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2854	/		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	0200	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.5	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	0643	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.5	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000			As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3888	1010	1010 /	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3312	1005			
	A/S	9	0083	/		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	0206	20	21		
	UP2S	82	0192	9	10		
3N02	UIRS	83	0020	-340	1558		
	UP1Z	84	0151	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	0145	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	0024	3N02		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2652	9	10.5	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2672	10		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000	3N02		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	120	3	-13	Spitting!	
	LP2S	92	0014	-50	-34	See pent-out!	
	LIRS	93	0002	3N02			
	LP1Z	94	0150	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	00163	/	SPIKING	Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	0001	3N02	"	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2804	3	11.1	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2757	5	"	As IAT	
	LIRT	99	1210	3N02	"	As IAT	
	J/W	42	0947	-0.1		As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	2713	8.2	8.6		
	HYCC	59	0708	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	4095			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	2947	9.5	9.6		
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	2506	10	9.6	same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	2819				
	HEIM	141	2408				
	PRTC	142	2379	/		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	3404			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	0041	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0154				
	O3P	106	2041	961.4	-	P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145m.B	
	O3RG	113	1516				
0702							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0703	FL NO	1	Hex	0533	A533	CF	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0070	070349		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0349		✓	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	07-9	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec	'			Multipxd Hkeeping
3226 10.6	1452 3855	3222	0811	3226	3735	3226	0141
	LATC	160	Dec	0586	51.56	✓ ?	Latitude
	LONG	161	Dec	4043	-4.216	✓	Longitude
0706							

RESET.

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

PRE FLIGHT

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0706	TWCD	70	4051	—		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	963	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0043	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2300	-low?		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2237	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2079	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2119	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4098			4095	
	EV1V	170	2043				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3486				
	EVIC	173	3968				
07	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: 4533

Date: 050497

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0827	REF +	5	0567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2854	/		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	1941	F/S / O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	0464	F/S / O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095	FL130		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	2377	13.3	FL135 /	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3253	480			
	A/S	9	1191	170	/	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	0475	390	320		
	UP2S	82	6900	111	107		
	UIRS	83	607	-282	1550 3NO2		
	UP1Z	84	156	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	151	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	667	/	3NO2	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	3023	-8	-4.5	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	3023	-8		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000		3NO2	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	1280	723	249	SPIKING	
	LP2S	92	956	193	94	"	
	LIRS	93	0900	-231	112 3NO2		
	LP1Z	94	3019	X SPIKING		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	624	X "		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	1525	X	3NO2	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	3350	-22	-2	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	3349	-22		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0971	97	3NO2	As IAT	
	J/W	42	1190	0.1	0.04	As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	1733	-23	-23.7		
	HYCC	59	0752	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1323	-33.8		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	977				
	DTF	10	2238	-9			
	DTC	11	1+		-8.2		
	NDTF	23	1988	-8		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	2686				
	HEIM	141	1383				
	PRTC	142	2378	/		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	1150			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1083			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0215				
	O3P	106	1884	90.6		P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145mB	
	O3RG	113	1741				
0856							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0104	FL NO	1	Hex	0533	A533	✓	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0090	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0645	/	090445	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0016	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
2358 -11-05	3254 / 1224 /	2360	1452	2357	3792 ✓	2360	0173 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	0636	55.968N	✓	Latitude
	LONGC	161	Dec	3443	-8.616	✓	Longitude
0410							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

L 2500

R 2250

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL200

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1050	TWCD	70	1167	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2511	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1200	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2578	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2252	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	0610	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1472	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1020	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170	3476				
	EV2V	171	3137				
	NPWR	172	2705				
	EVIC	173	4019				
1058	EV2C	174	4001				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

7
3822
2442

Flight No: A 533 Date: 050491

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CHEK for auto selection

FL200

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1140	REF +	5	567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2853	/		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	1935	F/S / O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1747	F/S / O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095	FL200	/	As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	1793	20.0	FL200 /	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3070	935	/		
	A/S	9	2000	222	240 /	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	2310	768	780		
	UP2S	82	2003	372	416		
	UIRS	83	981	-205	1559		
	UP1Z	84	149	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	142	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	980	3N02		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2999	-6	-6.1	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	3016	-6		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000	3N02		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	4048	1570	529 / 0	SPITING	
	LP2S	92	1214	270	223 / 0	"	
	LIRS	93	867	3N02	-240	"	
	LP1Z	94	496			Approx 0150 "	
	LP2Z	95	268			Approx 0146 "	
	LIRZ	96	896	3N02		Approx 2050 "	
	LP1T	97	2994	-6	-6	As IAT "	
	LP2T	98	3005	-6		As IAT "	
	LIRT	99	257	3N02		As IAT "	
	J/W	42	1071	0	-0.03	As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	1073	-45	-45		
	HYCC	59	894	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1099	-45	/	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	929				
	DTF	10	2979	-6			
	DTC	11	4				
	NDTF	23	2671	-6		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	2601				
	HEIM	141	2095				
	PRTC	142	2378	/		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	1189	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1329			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	225				
	O3P	106	1895	903		P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145mB	
	O3RG	113	1874				
1211							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1217	FL NO	1	Hex	0533	A533		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	121			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	909	/		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0030	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
-12 2284	1252 3854	2284	1428	2286	3785	2291	173
	LATC	160	Dec	528	46.46		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3865	-19.88		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL200

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1226	TWCD	70	1222	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2506	/		2000-3460 < min	
	TSAM	72	1282	/		0640-1860 < min	
	TAMB	73	2566	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2222	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1959	/		0000-4095 < 4095	
	HTR2	76	1365	/		0000-4095 < 4095	
	ISRC	77	1017	/		0001-1230 < min	
	STAT	78	4095	/		4095	
	EV1V	170	3478				
	EV2V	171	3139				
	NPWR	172	2709				
	EVIC	173	4016				
1239	EV2C	174	4000				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

 Flight No **A 533**.....

 Date **05 04 97**.....

 Page **1**..... of **2**.....

Video Tape	
No. 11 16	
Ends A533#1	
(C) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	55° 30.61N	55° 30.56N
Long	004° 36.45W	004° 36.51W
Time	063156	063227
Status	OK	GCALIGN

DRS recording to HORACE	(y/n)
HORACE recording to disc	(y/n)
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
060502				DATA	ON				
074740				SET	TO	NAV			
080845				TAKE	OFF	PRESTWICH			
				START	RUN 1		Wet chemistry run.		
081412	11	4000	1009	250	190	3.2	4.4	OFF	308/29
				END	RUN 1				
081917	12	4000	1009	280	190	4.1	5.8	OFF	300/27
				START	RUN 2				
082330	13	FL 085	1013	295	180	0.2	-0.7	OFF	300/28
				END	RUN 2				
082503	14	FL 085	1013	300	180	0.1	-0.1	OFF	300/27
				climb	to avoid		cloud.		
				START	RUN 3				
083644	15	FL 160	1013	305	180	-14.9	-17.8	OFF	300/31
				END	RUN 3				
085854	16	FL 160	1013	290	185	-14.8	-22.3	OFF	296/33
				START	P1				1000 FPM
090926	17	F160	1013	290	180	-13.4	-24.6	OFF	294/33
091531	18	8000	1006	290	185	0.6	-1.2	OFF	293/21 500 FPM
				B					

Video Tape

No. A53341
Ends 1146

FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	56° 00.2N	55° 59.56N
Long	10° 02.36W	10° 05.72W
Time	09 2203	
Status	CR	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE y/n

HORACE recording to disc y/n

SATCOM sending pos reports (y/n)

R4.

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				END	PI					
042800	19	900	1015	270	180	8.4	9.7	OFF		/
										SS-
				START	Run 4					
042818	20	1000	1015	270	180	8.4	9.8	OFF		285/21
										500 800 FPM
				END	Run 4	START P2.1			↗	
093717	21	1000	1015	270	180	8.4	9.8	OFF		285/21
				END	P2.1	//	START	Run 5	↗	
094444	22	FL050	1013	270	185	4.4	4.5	OFF		293/22
				END	R5	//	START	P2.2	↗	1000 FPM
045152	23	FL050	1013	270	180	4.6	5.1	OFF		290/22
				END	P2.2	//	START	R6.1	↗	
045650	24	FL100	1013	270	180	-2.3	-4.2	OFF		289/24
				END	R6.1	//	START	R6.2		
100348	25	FL100	1013	270	180	-2.8	-3.4	OFF		289/23
				END	R6.2	//	START	P2.3		1000 FPM
101012	26	FL100	1013	265	190	-3.5	-3.9	OFF		288/24
				END	P2.3	//	START	R6.3	↗	
101513	27	FL150	1013	265	190	-13.1	-12.8	OFF		267/24
				END	R6.3	//	START	P2.4		1000 FPM
102012	28	FL150	1013	265	190	-12.2	-14.7	OFF		267/23
				Accelerate to	make	Oceanic	Boundary			
				END	P2.4	//	START	R8		
102627	29	FL200	1013	270	180	-20.3	-36.1	OFF		273/36

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 533.....

Date 0504 97.....

Page 2 of 2.....

Video Tape
 Io. AS33 #1
 Ends CHANGED @ 1400.
 FC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	54° 52.26N	54° 49.18N
Long	015° 02.45W	015° 04.45W
Time	1028 50	1029
Status	OK	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE (y/n)
HORACE recording to disc (y/n)
SATCOM sending pos. reports (y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			END	RUN 8					
04337	30	FL200	1013	225	220	-19.8	-41.5	OFF	275/30
				TRANSIT TO SANTA MARIA					
				VIDEO TAPE PAUSED.					
				START RUN 9.					
32441	31	FL200	1013	200	230	-22.3	-32.6	OFF	125/9
				VIDEO RESTARTED.					
				END RUN 9					
34433	32	FL200	1013	230	230	-22.9	-30.4	OFF	101/9
				START P 3-1					
34523	33	FL200	1013	225	280	-21.8	-28.8	OFF	102/8
				END P 3-1	//		START R 10		
35006	34	FL150	1013	225	180	-12.4	-16.9	OFF	094/5
				END RUN 10	/		START P 3-2		
35646	35	FL150	1013	225	180	-12.3	-17.0	OFF	113/4
				END P 3-2	//		START R 11		
140135	36	FL100	1013	230	180	-1.4	-5.0	OFF	095/03
				END RUN 11	//		START P 3-3		1000 hr
140851	37	FL100	1013	223	180	-0.1	-4.9	OFF	098/5

Video Tape

No. A533 #2
Ends 1700

FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	38° 38.76N	38° 36.15N
Long	24° 28.53W	24° 31.35W
Time	14 10 36	14 1104
Status	OK	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE (y/n)

HORACE recording to disc (y/n)

SATCOM sending pos reports (y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				END	P3.3	//	START	R 12.	
141254	38	6000	1016	230	180	9.4	-1.4	OFF	083/4
				END	R12	//	START	P3.4	1000/m
143231	40	6000	1017	240	185	9.8	-2.6	OFF	103/8
				END	P3.4	//	START	R13	+
143514	41	3500	1018.5	180	180	13.4	-1.2	OFF	083/9
				END	RUN	13	//	START	P3.5
144055	42	3500	1015	180	180	11.6	0.8	OFF	500/m 068/9
				END	P3.5	//	START	R14	SS=4
144717	43	5000	1016	175	180	15.5	13.2	OFF	022/7
				START	RUN	14			
144822	45	1000	1016	110	180	15.5	12.4	OFF	029/7
				END	RUN	14			
145804	46	1000	1016	110	180	15.6	13.0	OFF	028/7
150730				LAND	SANTA	MARIA			
				HOLD	Ht		36° 52.30N		
							025° 09.85W		
152222				DATA	OFF				

Search Flight

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A533

DATE: 05 104 197

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	/ // // /		
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	/ // // // / // // // / // // /		
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	/ / SNOR / / SNOR X X X X		
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	/ // /		
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	X X / X X		

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

CARRIER GAS 5% METHANE IN ARGON
HUMIDIFIED BY $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A 533Project ACSOEDate 0504 97Tape No A533#1 User KATERetention Period 10 YRS

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
0816	0	FFC	Run 1. 4000'
0823			Run 2 FL085
0836			Run 3 FL160
0908			PROF1 FL160 → 900 ^{RL}
0928			Run 4 1000 ^{RL}
0944			Run 5 FL050
0956			Run 6.1 FL100
1003			Run 6.2 FL100
1015			Run 7 FL150
1026			Run 8 FL200
1045			TAPE PAUSED
1324.			Run 9 FL200 TAPE RESTARTED
1350			Run 10 FL150.
1401			Run 11 FL100. CHANGE TAPE

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. AS33

Date 5/4/97

Sheet no. 1

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Fill press. Frame	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
1	R10	7.2 bar		1000'	092817	093100	093128	978	Run 4
2	R30	7.2 bar		5000'	094630 094748	094718 0948	094826	843	Run 5
3	R36	7.1 bar 6.9 bar		10000'	095714	100400	100507	697	Run 6.2
4	R6	6.9 bar		15000'	101514	101655	101904	571	Run 7
5	R8	5.4 bar		20000'	102638	102833	103057	465	Run 8
6	R 2	5.25		20000'	134015	134210	134412	467	Run 9
7	H3 R10	6.9		15000'	135020	135152	135400	572	Run 10
8	R29	7.1		10000' 140154	140154 140340	140340	140444	698	Run 11
9	R4	7.2		6000'	141400	141500	141540	817	Run 12
10	R37	7.2		3500'	143520	143700	143732	894	Run 13
11	R12	7.2		100'	144820	145014	145040	1013	Run 14

BAG Fillers Log

Flight No

Date

Operator

AS33

5/4/97

Dave T

V1

Time Start	Bag No	Event End	Height	Run	Comments
093250	231	093308	1000'	Run 4	
094926	234	094926	5000'	Run 5	
100578	232	100552	10000'	Run 6.2	
101720	235	101750	15000'	Run 7	
102907	233	102942	20000'	Run 8	
104500	S14	104538	20000'	Transit	
110056	S17	110140	20000'	Transit	
111917	S15	112007	"	"	
113405	S21	113446	"	"	
114844	S38	114939	"	"	
120445	S13	120555	"	"	
121846	S16	12 18 ¹⁹ 46	"	"	
123340	1024	123430	"	"	
124850	1025	124938	"	"	
130339	84	130421	"	"	
131904	62	132000	"	"	
133220	82	133307	"	"	
134545	171	134620	"	R9/P3.1	PROFILE JUST STARTED
135210	S2	135242	15000'	R10	
14 05 ⁰⁴ 54	1026	140429	10000'	Run 11	
141508	172	141537	6000'	Run 12	
143746	154	143803	3500'	Run 13	
145050	153	145105	100'	Run 14	

Instrument Log Sheet: Pemali

Flight No: 533

Date: 5/4/97

Page: 1/1

Campaign: ACSOZ/MORE Operator(s): BSS

T/Ans: 7

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
			Zero	Wdts A = 620 B = 620
06:58			Cal	Wdts 1.22 HU B 1.21 30 Layer DES D 240 is A & B " 245 A & B 1.4 L/min Pensable Run @ 40 setting
07:08:35				Pen Change
07:53:20			Zero on	lidat volume
08:13	4000'		Zero on	End of Plotch
08:14	4000'	Run 2	Zero off	
8:16:40				Response to Zero of Nibir ⇒ 160 sec lag, H ₂ 190 sec lag O ₂
08:19:17		Circle		
	↑			Wind ≈ 6000'
08:23:29	8500'	Run 2		
08:24:16			Zero on	Cloudy bc get out of cloud
08:25:03		Run 2		
08:27			Zero off	Zero A & B .04
08:36:49	16000'	START Run 3		
08:39			Zero on	
08:42			Zero off	
08:46	16000'			1.4 L/min direct w
08:58:54	16000'	End 3		Scale descent 12,000'
	↓	St P		
09:08:25		St P ₁		from 16000 @ 1000'/min
09:15:31	8700'			500'/min Descent
09:22	4500'	↓		

Instrument Log Sheet: 1102

Flight No: S33

Date: 5/4/97

Page: 2 / 1

Campaign: ASPE (AZORA)
TLM 1102

Operator(s): RSB

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
0926	2000'	EP1	M	1.4 L/min Air Flow
0928	1000'	SR4		
09		ER4+		In Cloud
0937 17		SP2.1		Cloud @ 500' / min
093717	5000'			
094444	5100'	SR5		
095151		ER5		
	10000' $\uparrow$	SP2.2		Cloud @ 1000' / min In & out cloud
09520				Near dead tops
095649		End P27		
+ $\swarrow$	10000	SR6.1		Zeroing on Hecto / H ₂ O / 1000g
095700		Zero On		
100000		Zero Off		
100051		ER6.1		
		$\rightarrow$ SR6.2		Diter run
101013		ER6.2		
101013		SP2.3	To 15000'	1000' / min
101512		ER23		
101512	15000'	SR6.3		
102012		ER7		
	$\uparrow$	SP2.4		Accelerated up to 20000' & Thank to Alex @ warp Speed.
102140	16500			1.35 Titer Rate
	17500			1.28
	19000			1.2
102626	20000'	EP2.4		-15°C WIND 275° @ 66 kts
1032	20000		Zero On	
1035	20000		Zero Off	

Instrument Log Sheet: 1/20/02

Flight No: 533

Date: 5/4/97

Page: 3 / 1

Campaign: ACSCE / BLORES TRAVEL Operator(s): SR

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
122500	2000'		Zero on	2.3 @ 0.4 Vals.
122900	2000'		Zero off	1.15 L/min flow
<p>(Get pump and pan) (Andrew Key / K. Law)</p>				<p>Continuing Correlator 1-1 H_2O_2 mass / H_2O_2 meddion for period 10:35 - 1220 also regular correlation with O_3 re water vapour</p>
130120			Zero on	Zeroing constant
130420			Zero off	
132441	2000'	SR 9		Wanted green system for scope will have space of airplane
134624	2000'	ER 9		
134524	↓	SP 3.1		Probing in stratos for 50'
135006	15000'	EP 3.1		
135006		SR 10		Flow rate 1.4 L/min
135646	15000'	ER 10		
135646	↓	SP 3.2		(1.2 ppb H_2O_2 @ 15000')
140135		EP 3.2		
140135	10000'	SR 11		180 knots indicated speed
140850	10000'	ER 11		
140850	↓	SP 3.3		Flow rate 1.4 L/min
141255		EP 3.3		
141255	6000'	SR 12		
		ER 12		
141520			Zero on	0.04 (0.03)
142120			Zero off	
143231	6000'	ER 12		
143231	↓	SP 3.4		Descending to 3500'
1435		EP 3.4		

Instrument Log Sheet: Pearl

Flight No: 533

Date: 5/4/97

Page: 1/1

Campaign: AC302/MORE
TILANUS-17

Operator(s): BJS

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
			Zero	Mud A = 620 B = 620
06:58			Cal	Mud 1.22 Hu B 1.21 30 Layer
				DES D 240 is A & B
				" 245 A & B
				1.4 L/min
				Revised Run @ 40 salt
07:08:35				Level Change
07:53:30			Zero On	Level Volume
08:13	4000'		Zero On	End of Plot
08:14	4000'	Run 2	Zero off	
8:16:40				Response to level Nelson
				→ 160 sec lag, Ho ₂
				190 sec lag, Org
08:19:12		Level On		
	↑			Level ≈ 6000'
08:23:24	8500'	Run 2		
08:24:16			Zero On	Cloudy but get out of cloud
08:35:03		Cal 2		
08:27			Zero off	Zero A & B .04
08:36:44	16000'	START Run 3		
08:39			Zero On	
08:42			Zero off	
08:46	16000'			1.4 L/min in air
08:55:54	16000'	End 3		Stable descent to 1500'
	↓	St P		
09:08:25		St P ₁		from 16000 @ 1000'/min
09:15:31	8700'			500'/min Descent
09:22	4500'	↓		

Instrument Log Sheet: 1102

Flight No: S33

Date: 5/14/77

Page: 2 / 1

Campaign: ARCOE (ARCOE)
TILM517

Operator(s): RSS

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
0926	2000'	EB1	M	1.4 L/min Air Flow
0928	1000'	SR4		
09		ER4+		In Cloud
0937 ¹⁷		SP2.1		Cloudy @ 500' / min
093717	5000'			
094444	5100'	SR5		
095151		ER6		
	10000' ^A	SP2.2		Cloudy @ 1000' / min In & out cloud
09520				Near Lead Tops
095649		End P22		
+ 10000	10000	SR6.1		Zeroing on Heats 11/2 / 10000
095700		Zero On		
100000		Zero Off		
100051		ER6.1		
		SR6.2		Data run
101013		ER6.2		
101013		SP2.3	to 15000'	1000' / min
101512		ER2.3		
101512	15000'	SR7		
102012		ER7		
	^A	SP2.4		Accelerated up to 20000' & Turned to Altimeter @ warp Speed.
10:21 4)	16500			1.35 True Rate
	17500			1.28
	19000			1.2
102626	20000'	ER2.4		-15°C Wind 275° @ 66 kts
1032	20000		Zero On	
1035	20000		Zero Off	

Instrument Log Sheet: H₂O

Flight No: 533

Date: 5/4/97

Page: 3 / 1

Campaign: ACS of Aerosols TLM07 Operator(s): SR

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
122500	2000'		Zero on	2.3 @ 0.4 Vals.
122900	2000'		Zero off	1.15 L/min flow
<p>(Get pump and flow) (Andrew Key / K. Law)</p>				<p>Interesting Correlation 1.1 H_2O_2 mass / H_2O_2 molecules from 10:35 - 1220 also regular correlation with O_3 of water vapour</p>
130120			Zero on	Zero very consistent
130420			Zero off	
132441	2000'	SR 9		Would open system H_2O_2 with faster speed of airplane
134624	2000'	ER 9		
134524	↓	SP 3.1		Probing as starts for 50'
135006	15000'	EP 3.1		
135006		SR 10		Flow rate 1.4 L/min
135646	15000'	ER 10		
135646	↓	SP 3.2		(1.2 μ b H_2O @ 15000')
140135		EP 3.2		
140135	10000'	SR 11		@ 180 knots indicated speed
140850	10000'	ER 11		
140850	↓	SP 3.3		Flow rate 1.4 L/min
141255		EP 3.3		
141255	6000'	SR 12		
		ER 12		
1414520			Zero on	^B 0.04 ^A 10.03
1421.20			Zero off	
143231	6000'	ER 12		
143231	↓	SP 3.4		Descending to 3500'
1435		EP 3.4		

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: A533					Operator: KENT / TIDDEMAN / RICHER					Date: 5/4/97			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = 8					Optimisation = 16				Optimisation = 11				INJECT 40 S (FLOWS NOT ADJUSTED FROM YESTERDAY - INCREASED WHY?)
			Back Flush = 33.53					Back Flush = 43.82				Back Flush = 36.29				
			Flow rate = 31.17					Flow rate = 33.38				Flow rate = 35.58				
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP	
1		4000f	315.05	1777				317.81	1679			311.85	1613			TO SHORT FOR GC'S
2	082605		315.05	2327	339	1243	27.2	313.91	2159	29.3	1286	311.05	1986	26.8	1321	R NOT CONST (NOT BAD THOUGH)
3	083726	FL160	315.05	2003	341	1196	27.5	314.33	1916	29.4	1230	311.45	1673	26.9	1262	CAD IN PRES) NOT GOOD! *
4	084731	FL160	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	311.85	1684	27.0	1268	NOISE
5	0914	FL160	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	NOISE
7	092855	FL160	/	/	/	/	/	314.45	2526	29.4	1339	311.6	2380	26.9	1375	CP = 1044 (CH2) (WONS OFF)
8	093122 094402	FL160	/	/	/	/	/	314.25	2220	/	/	311.85	2146	27.0	1333	CP = 1002
9	094507	FL150	/	/	/	/	28.1	314.75	2277	29.4	1298	/	/	/	/	
10	095720	FL160	/	/	/	/	28.4	315.15	2055	29.5	1281	312.35	1905	27.1	1316	CP = 975
11	100405	FL160	/	/	/	/	28.7	315.35	2042	29.5	1284	312.65	1950	27.1	1319	CP = 978
12	10531	FL160	/	/	/	/	29.1	315.75	1921	29.5	1255	313.15	1772	27.2	1288	CP = 947
13	102651	FL200	/	/	/	/	29.5	316.25	1788	29.6	1238	313.65	1652	27.3	1262	CP = 929
14	103525	FL200	/	/	/	/	30.2	316.55	1797			314.05	1580			AUTO MARKED CP = 926

* Very large water peak (+ change in inject time to 35s

▽ Actually an inject on ~~sample~~ channel 3 (by accident) during descent - 0925.06 ST SP 311.65 2303

CARRIER GAS 5% METHANE IN ARGON
HUMIDIFIED BY $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: AS33					Operator: KENT/RICHER/TUDENHATN					Date: 5/4/97			
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
			Optimisation = 8					Optimisation = 16				Optimisation = 11				
			Back Flush = 33.53					Back Flush = 43.82				Back Flush = 36.29				Inject = 35 s
			Flow rate = 31.77					Flow rate = 33.38				Flow rate = 35.58				
			ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP	
15	104402	FL200	/	/	/	/	20.2	316.85	1798	19.6	1240	314.25	1583	27.4	1281	
16	105234	FL200	/	/	/	/	/									
17	1101:16	FL200	/	/	/	27.2	20.2	317.05	1802	19.7	1246	314.45	1585	27.4	1283	
18	11:08:49	FL200	/	/	/	/	/	317.05	1802			314.45	1581			RUNTIME NPN 302 → 450
19	11:14:46	"	/	/	/	/	/	317.05	2447			/	/	/	/	CP = 936
20	113047	"	315.15	2585				317.05	2485			314.25	2326			INJECT 40s
21	114158	"	315.15	2585				316.90	780			314.15	658			DISCOUNT
22	114946	"	315.75	1838				316.75	1830			314.05	1689			CP 935
23	115732	"	315.15	184				316.05	1831			313.05	1690			
24	120520	"	/	/	/	/	21.3	316.55	1831	21.6	1248	313.75	1693	27.2	1283	
25	121308	"	315.15	/	/	/	/	316.35	1833			313.55	1690			
26	122053	"	/	/	/	/	/	316.25	1828							
27	122840	"	/	/	/	/	/	316.25	1828			313.45	1687			

* SAMPLE TAKEN TOO EARLY DISCOUNT

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record		Flight Number: AS33				Operator: RUCHER / TTDOMAN / KONT-Date: 27/4/97									
Sample	Time	Channel 1				Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments	
No.	Height	ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP	
28	123628 FL200						31615	1826			31325	1690			
29	124416 FL200						31605	1828			31315	1689			
30	125202 FL200						31595	1832			31305	1690			NOISE
31	125949 FL200						31585	1831	2.5	11.4	3295	1690	27.1	284	NOISE
32	130736 FL200						31575	1834			31295	1691			
33	131523 FL200						31565	1833			3279	1698			
34	132310 FL200						31555	1837			3215	1700			
35	13308 FL200						31545	1836			31245	1701			
36	133903 FL200						31525	1839	8.4	22.0	31225	1702	22.0	1274	PROBABLE CHANGE END OF GC
37	135028 FL150						31505	1977	29.5	1236	31205	1840	27.0	1274	CP = 935
38	140218 FL100						31485	2175			3195	203	13.7	1357	CP = 1015 *
39	14113 6000ft														CP = 1042
40	141849						NOT	FUNCTIONING							

1310 O₃ + NO_y elevated. * channel 2 not working.

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
4 1 1	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
1 or 3 2 or 3 2 2	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
2 1 1 4	SAFIRE log MISSION SCIENTIST OCN log BOTTLES MARSS log BAGS DEIMOS log PAN GC's Chemistry log
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
1	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

RS

A533 05-APR-97 13:29:51 031 Q 41.06 -22.66 FC F

HQG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
188.	467.	19.9	310.	-22.6	-33.3	117/8

GE DEWP -33.31 H202 MR 0.35

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VTDF	HELP

P3 ↓

A533

05-APR-97

15:03:39

046 Ω

36.81

-25.00 RV P

HDG deg T 290.	SPR mb 985.	PHGT kft 0.8	TAS knots 155.	TAT C 13.3	DEW C 12.0	WIND deg m/s 041/10	
----------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	------------------	------------------	---------------------------	--

PRES HGT 239.94 m OZONE MR 0.00 PPb NOXY NOY 0.42
 2.22 33.33 55.57 100.00 133.33 155.67
 10000.00 10000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SEL-FCI	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

P31

A533 05-APR-97 14:43:12 042 Ω 37.13 -25.51 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
156.	939.	2.1	186.	9.5	10.2	036/7

OZONE MR 49.32 NOXY NOY 3.45

A B C D E F G H
 SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM WIDED HELP

R8

A533 05-APR-97 13:23:39 030 Ω 41.58 -22.52 RV P

HDG deg T 188.	SPR mb 467.	PHGT kft 19.9	TAS knots 309.	TAT C -22.2	DEW C -34.2	WIND deg m/s 127/9
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OZONE NR 60.55 NOXY NOY 2.33

125.00 100.00 75.00 50.00 25.00 0.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

28

A533 05-APR-97 12:51:15 030 Ω 44.21 -21.33 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
196	465	20.0	307	-19.5	-37.4	097 / 9

H202 MR 0.30 MOD H202 0.27
 p.p.s p.p.c

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

Cl_2O_3 / H_2O_2 Per Seum passed
1) Remains H_2O_2 measured off at with time
2) of water vapor

A533 05-APR-97 12:22:30 030 Ω 46.48 -20.17 RV P

28

HDG deg 199.	SPR mb 465.	PHGT kft 20.0	TAS knots 304.	TAT C -19.3	DEW C -33.9	WIND deg 127 / 9
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H202 NR 0.22 MOD H202 0.35
 9.96
 1.35

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		STAF		HEAD

R8

A533 05-APR-97 12:37:03 030 Ω 45.34 -20.77 RY P

HWD deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
195.	465.	20.0	306.	-19.2	-34.6	122 / 9

TWC DEWP -29.24 TATND -19.59

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO		HELP

R8 (F200)

A533 05-APR-97 13:26:21 031 Ω 41.35 -22.58 RV P

HDG deg 188.	SPR mb 467.	PHGT kft 19.9	TAS knts 308.	TAT C -22.3	DEW C -33.1	WIND deg 123/ 8
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H202 MR 0.39 MOD H202 0.55
 0.55 0.39

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

08

A533 05-APR-97 12:25:51 030 Ω 46.23 -20.33 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
199.	465.	20:0	305.	-19.3	-33.9	120/10

OZONE MR 55.37 MOD H202 0.35
 9.99
 125.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WTRFO	CHERD

08

A533 05-APR-97 13:00:42 030 Ω 43.44 -21.71 RV P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg T	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
196.	465.	20.0	309.	-20.3	-40.2	106/16

OZONE MR 30.05 H2O2 MR 0.21
 ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

R8

A533 05-APR-97 12:30:18 030 Ω 45.88 -20.51 RY P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
195.	465.	20.0	307.	-19.7	-32.0	118/10

GE TEMP -32.24 MOD -202 0.43

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SECT	PARAS	FRQ	700M			VIDEO	CHETA

P3↓

A533 05-APR-97 14:30:00 039 Ω 37.79 -25.48 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
230.	817.	5.9	200.	9.3	-1.9	104/8

H202 MR 1.46 MOD H202 4.33
 3.50 3.00 4.00 3.00 3.00 1.00 0.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO		HF P

A533 05-APR-97 14:31:54 039 Ω 37.72 -25.59 RV P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
226.	816.	5.9	193.	9.5	-2.1	107/ 8

H2O2 MR 1.43 MOD H2O2 4.23
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

P3↓ (starts 13.45)

A533 05-APR-97 14:14:09 038 Ω 38.45 -24.66 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
218.	818.	5.8	196.	9.2	-2.0	085/ 9

OZONE MR 51.72 H2O2 MR 1.50
 99.9
 125.00

A SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM
 B
 C
 D ZOOM
 E
 F VIDEO
 G
 H HELP

12

A533 05-APR-97 10:45:36 030 Ω 53.67 -15.89 RV P

HDG degT 211.	SPR mb 465.	PHGT kft 20.0	TAS knots 303.	TAT C -20.1	DEW C -41.1	WIND deg m/s 273/30
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10000.00 1.00 1.00 1.00 1.00 1.00 1.00
 8000.00 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67
 6000.00 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67
 4000.00 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67
 2000.00 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67
 0.00 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67 1.67

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

P2 ↑ 09.37 → 10.20

A533 05-APR-97 10:30:39 029 Ω 54.74 -15.17 RV P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg T	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
216.	466.	20.0	292.	-19.8	-40.1	276/34

PRES HGT 5089.77 m OZONE MR 59.75 ppb H2O2 MR 0.13 ppb
0.00 25.00 50.00 75.00 100.00 125.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A533 05-APR-97 08:50:30 015 -- 55.75 -7.53 AS P

291.	549.	16.0	220.	-14.7	-25.3	293/33
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---	---	---	---	---	---	---

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A533 05-APR-97 10:38:15 029 Ω 54.20 -15.53 RV P

HDG deg 212.	SPR mb 465.	PHGT kft 20.0	TAS knots 304.	TAT C -20.3	DEW C -39.2	WIND deg 270/31
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PRES HGT 5103.35 m NOXY NOY 0.00 OZONE MR 20.84 %
 2.20 0.50 1.00 1.50 2.00 2.50
 10000.00 8000.00 6000.00 4000.00 2000.00 0.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A533

05-APR-97

10:41:09

029 Ω

53.99

-15.67 RV P

HDG deg T 211.	SPR mb 465.	PHGT kft 20.0	TAS knots 300.	TAT C -20.0	DEW C -40.9	WIND deg m/s 273/29
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CZONE
ccc

50.14

NOVY NOVY

0.27

125.00

100.00

75.00

50.00

25.00

0.00

0.00

0.25

0.50

0.75

1.00

1.25

125.00

100.00

75.00

50.00

25.00

0.00

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A533

05-APR-97

09:28:30

020 Ω

55.92

-10.54 RV P

HDG deg 259.	SPR mb 978.	PHGT kft 1.0	TAS knots 182.	TAT C 8.4	DEW C 9.9	WIND deg m/s 283/19
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PRESS TGT 2000.00 m DEONE MF 45.99 888 H202 MF 0.16 PPb
 0.00 33.33 33.33 100.00 133.33 10000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A533 05-APR-97 10:53:48 030 Ω 53:08 -16.28 RV P

HDT deg T 211.	SPR mb 465.	PHGT k ft 20.0	TAS knots 301.	TAT C -18.7	DEM C -45.7	WIND deg m/s 266/27
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OZONE ppb 33.08 H2O2 MR ppb 0.08

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

INPUT WEIGHT & FUEL SUMMARY

Computed for Met Research Flight by C F P

Max TOW = 155000 lbs Max LW = 135000 lbs
 ZFW = 98000 lbs
 Ramp Fuel = 54000 lbs
 Start/Taxy = 5400 lbs
 Min Div = 3000 lbs
 Overhead = 5500 lbs
 Hold FF = 4500 lbs
 Contingency = 5 %
 Extra Fuel = 0 lbs

Weather:

Dep: EGPK Elev: 00066' Des: LPAZ Elev: 00308'
 R/W: OAT: QNH: E/W: OAT: QNH:
 W/V: QFE: W/V: QFE:
 Wx: SALT: Wx: SALT:
 Cloud: Cloud:

Hercules-W2 ODM Computed.CCP. VNO 1

From EGPK To LPAZ C/S Crew Date 04 04 97

WPT	Lvl	W/V	ISA	Tkt	Tkm	Dr	TAS	GrS	DIS	EET	ETA	ATA	TET	FU	Rmg	FF(k)	DTC
EGPK															48600		1536
PW	ASC	C-50	+3	304	311	+0	190	140	4	2			0.02				1532
LOITER	ASC	C-50	+3	000	007	+0	190	140	0	0			0.02				1532
TOC	ASC	C-50	+3	281	288	+0	190	140	19	8			0.10	1275	47325	7.7	1511
56N10W	120	C-50	+3	281	288	+0	307	257	163	38			1.25 1.25	4193	43132	6.6	1350
55N15W	200	C-20	+3	253	263	+0	309	289	180	37 37			1.25	3411	39721	5.5	1170
50N18W	200	C-20	+3	201	212	+0	311	291	319	66			2.31	6022	33699	5.5	851
45N21W	200	C-20	+3	203	214	+0	314	294	324	66			3.37	6087	27612	5.5	527
40N23W	200	C-10	+3	201	212	+0	317	307	256	50			4.27	4606	23006	5.5	271
LOITER										2			4.29	167	22839	5.0	271
DELTAR	200	C-10	+3	195	206	+0	318	308	200	39			5.08	3587	19252	5.5	71
VSM	120	C-10	+3	227	238	+0	314	304	71	14			5.22	1544	17708	6.6	0
LPAZ	120	C-10	+3	000	012	+0	314	304	0	0			5.22	0	17708	6.6	0
Diversion																	
										Totals							
LPLA	270	C-10	+3	320	332				141	37				3032	14676		

FUEL SUMMARY

lbs

Start/Taxy : 5400 T/O Fuel : 48600
 Plan Fuel : 30892 Plan Fuel : 30892
 Diversion : 3032 Actu Reserve : 17708
 Min Overhead : 5500 Hold Fuel : 4500
 Contingency : 1545 Rsv Endurance : 3.56
 Extra Fuel : 0 Flt Plan Time : 5.22
 Req'd Start Fuel: 46369 Total Endurance : 9.33

WEIGHT SUMMARY

lbs

ZFW : 98000
 Ramp Fuel : 54000
 Ramp Weight : 152000
 Take Off Weight : 146600
 Landing Weight : 115708

(c) RJCV 1991

WAYPOINTS

1	EGPK	00066'	N5530.2	W00434.5	①
	PW	426.00	N5532.7	W00440.9	
2	56N10W		N5530.0	W01000.0	②
	55N15W		N5530.0	W01500.0	③
	50N18W		N5530.0	W01800.0	④
	45N21W		N4530.0	W02100.0	⑤
	40N23W		N4030.0	W02300.0	⑥
	DELTAR		N330.0	W02405.0	⑦
	VSM	113.70	N3657.7	W02510.0	⑧
	LPAZ	00308'	N3658.0	W02510.0	⑧
	LPLA	00180'	N3845.0	W02705.5	⑨

OBSERVATIONS

NOxy Instrument Pre-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A533

Date: 5th APRIL '97

Page: 1/1

Campaign: OXICOA/AZORES Operator(s): TIM GREEN.

200L
 TIME
 (PT+1)

 200L
 TIME
 (PT+1)

Time (GMT)	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments
04 41						COOLERS FULL - SYSTEM 'ON'
04 57		164	332	200	100	BKGD COUNTS FOR PMT'S
05.01		959	3168	16133	7792	OZONE/2ERS 'ON' PMT'S COUNTS.
05.08						INLETS REACHED ~600°C
05.36		539	2306	17698	32903	BKGD COUNTS PMT'S STABLE
06.39	SNOOPER #1 @ Cal.	801	15000	/	/	? LOOKED OK TO ME
		48000	1854	/	/	
06.50.	SNOOPER #2 @ Cal.	1200	68500	/	/	
		53700	570.	/	/	
0606	CO LS content gauge @ ~ 550					psig (↔ N15L)
0612						NOy converters down to 300°C (x 1/2)
0618	WARMUP	on SNOOPER #1				(sequenced) aborted
0620	CAL	(manual)				on NO & NO2 snoooper #1
0624	WARMUP	sequence on snoooper #1				
0642	CAL	46800	49500			NO sens. = 7.7 cnts/ppt
	ZERO	700	1800			NO2 sens. = 8.0 cnts/ppt
0647	CAL			41800	36800	NOy1 sens = 6.8 cnts/ppt
	ZERO			1100	680	NOy2 sens = 6.1 cnts/ppt
0651	all manual CAL off					
0652	warm-up sequences off					
0657	WARM-UP sequences on without CAL to check artifacts					
	MEAS.	450	2100	1850	1200	NO artif. = 3 ppt ✓ ok
	ZERO	430	1750	800	650	NO2 artif = 44 ppt ✓ ok
						NOy1 artif = 16 ppt ✓ → MDC 6.005 → 200L?
						NOy2 artif = 90 ppt ✓ GOOD
0710	ran out of GND ZFA → switch to A/C ZFA tank → slight contamination @ inlet					
	warm up sequences off.					
0729	inlet heaters on → slight rise of NOy 2 cnts					
0732	O3 HV off preparing for shutdown to power saver					
0737	system ready for power saver (all gases off + rec off)					
0748	start of OTC (O2as turbine compressor) on A/C					
0753	GND A/C engine started → power saver					

NOy 0.5% = [NOy]

200L?

Note: All times logged as GMT

Delivery Gases (Gnd-A/C) Change Over Time: 0710

Power Change Over Time: 0753

Can Flush On: N/A

NB not used to save ZA. ↑

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: AS33

Date: 5/4/97

Page: 1/14

Campaign: ACEE/MORE

Operator(s): Ryanville/Green

Take-Off Time: 0809

Can Flush Off: N/A

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
0800	GND						NOxy ready for +/0. 7min required for starting up NOxy after power switch on.	
0803	ARTIF	started					sequenced.	
0814	1st 2'	measure'					check made for N 0809 on NOy cuts, NOy artifact show spikes → (contaminant or electronic noise)	
081412	4000						start of Run 1	
							→ scanned during +/0 → might be due to leak @ 130 took off right behind 737 → load of NOxy (AN flush was off end of Run 1)	
081917								
0819							→ NOxy on ambient air	
082330	8500						start of Run 2	
082503	8500						end of Run 2	
083149	16000						start of Run 3	
0838							start of NOy & NO cal not sequenced → ~18min	
083854	16000						end of Run 3	
0855							→ latent zero (for NO cleaned)	
0906	16000	ZERO	350	1402	700	470	not sequenced.	Z
0907	16000	ZERO						
090826	16000 ↓						start of profile 1	
0923							ambient concentrations for NOy1: 0.4V → ~760ppb NOy2: 0.1V → ~260ppb	
092800	1000						end of F1	
092818	1000						start of Run 4	
0929	1000	ZERO	350	1200	600	350	not sequenced	Z
							end of Run 4	
093717	45000						start of P2.1	
094441	5000						start of Run 5	
0945	5000	ZERO	300	1350	570	350	not sequenced	Z
095152	5000						end of Run 5	
	↑10000						start of Run 2.2	

Note: All times logged as GMT

NOxy PARAMETERS ON HERACE

NO → 630
NO2 → 631
NOy1 → 632
NOy2 → 633

39
70
57
+ 3
900

NO_x Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A533 Date: 5/4/97 Page: 214
 Campaign: ACSDE/AZOREs Operator(s): Bauswitz
 Take-Off Time: 0809 Can Flush Off: N/A

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO ₂ (cps)	NO _y 1 (cps)	NO _y 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
095650	10000						end of P 2.2	
0957	10000	ZERO	310	1400	600	340	start of Run 6.1	Z
			↳ not sequenced				end of R 6.1	
1003							start of R 6.2	
101010	↑ 15000						end of R 6.2	
							start of P 2.3	
NB: for last 4		zeros (Z)		clutter of NO ₂ & bays		won't off		
101513	15000						end of P 3.1 start of R 7.7	
101545	15000	ZERO	370	1380	650	380	not sequenced, w/ clutter	Z'
							off.	
102012	↑ 20000						end of R 7.2 start of P 2.4	
102627	20000						start of R.8	
1027	20000	ZERO	400	1500	800	440	not sequenced, clutter off	Z'
NB: for last 6		zeros (Z & Z')		bypass on bay		not used.		
1038	A/C man @ 300 kts speed transitioning to 12000' @ 20,000'							
1041	20000	ZERO	450	1450	800	450	using new sequence	Z
NB: new zero sequence		is for 1 min 30 sec.		Sequence includes		end of Run 8'		by pass
1043								
1045	NO ₂ flux Press @ 286 torr							
1102	20000	ZERO					sequenced (w/ repeat time set @ 15 min)	
1117	20000	ZERO			700	350	sequenced	
$V = \frac{[(\text{Raw cuts} - \text{zero cuts}) / \text{SENS}]}{\text{ppmV}} \times \frac{\text{ppmV}}{2000} \times V$								

Note: All times logged as GMT

O₃ on HORACE → 574 total H₂O content 572 591 Dewpt TW

NOxy Instrument In-Flight Log Sheet

Flight No: A533

Date: 5/4/97 Page: 314

Campaign: ACSDE/AZORE

Operator(s): Banyette

Take-Off Time: 0809

Can Flush Off: N/A

Note: Enter Sequence (SEQ.) as Calib, Zero, Artifact

Time (GMT)	Altitude	SEQ.	NO (cps)	NO2 (cps)	NOy 1 (cps)	NOy 2 (cps)	Comments	Run
12 17	20000	ZERO	450	1400	550	370	sequenced	
12 21	20000		NO output to DRS w zero value above + 2.5V/cuts as scaling factor -					
12 29			NO output to DRS set @					
12 44	<u>NS</u>		NOy 1 on HORACE is actually NO2 from NOxy					
			NO (NOxy) displayed @ approx. 100 pptv for 10V					
			NO2 (NOxy) displayed @ approx. 500 pptv for 10V					
12 50			NOy 1 (NOxy) 1000 pptv for 10V					
			NOy 2 (NOxy) 1000 pptv for 10V					
13 24 41	20000	CR	start of R9					
13 28	20000	CR	(NO2 cal & NO cal on) not sequenced still pb w (chumbo)					
13 44 33	20000		end of R9 NOy 1 cal.					
13 45 23	↓		start of P3.1					
→ 13 42			→ we sequenced zero for next stack					
13 46	15000		end of P3.1 / start of Run 10					
13 50 06								
13 56 46	↓		end of R10 / start of P3.2					
14 01	10000	ZERO	370	1200	450	230	sequenced	
14 02 35	10000		start of R11 / end of P3.2					
14 08 54	↓		end of R11 / start of P3.3					
			New zero values fed to converters for DRS					
14 12 58	6000		end of P3.3 / start of R12					
14 17	6000		zero sequence accidentally on during R12 (during measurement) - CR NS					
14 21	6000	ZERO	390	1320	460	240	sequenced	
14 32 31	↓		end of Run 12 / start of P3.4					
14 35 19	3500		start of R13 / end of P3.4					
14 40 55	↓		end of Run 13 / start of P3.5					

Note: All times logged as GMT

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A537

Date: 5/1/97

Page: 1 / 1 / 6

Campaign: Acson - TRANSIT A2000 Operator(s): M. Hsuy.

Air Sampling Rate: 1.54 SLM Peristaltic Pump Speed: 3 (rpm)
1mV = 7.5 ppmV.

PMT Sensitivity: 30 Calib Factor: ~~1.0~~ (V to ppt) 409.5 drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: 8.5 min Filtered React Coil Temp: 93°C

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
			CALIB. 1mV = 10.6 pptV @ 1 SLM @ 3A
			1mV = 7.5 pptV @ 1.5 SLM
			<u>Pre-Flight</u>
06:41:25	Z	0.71	
06:45:25	A	0.69	End zero - low noise but zero higher than expected.
06:48:00			Debubbler stopped working.
06:54:00	Z	0.98	Started zero.
07:06:49	Z	0.68	lamp = 7.14V
07:14:30	Z	0.67	
07:38:42	Z	0.65	0.65 ppbV on Brians PC
07:44:30	Z	0.64	
07:54:00	Z	0.67	power transfer complete left running on zero - During take off.
08:13:10	Z	0.64	climbing to 4000' (safety altitude)
08:14:12	A	0.68	Start Run ① - Bad blip on zero!
08:19:17	A	0.86	End of Run ①, climbing to 4000'
08:23:30	Z	0.68	At FL 85 RUN ② start
08:25:03	Z	0.70	Run ② started - climbed to avoid clouds.
08:25:41	A	0.71	Turned off zero
08:36:41	Z	0.742	Start Run ② @ FL 160. Scale rate = 0.77 SLM. Started zero
08:44:26	A	0.70	Sel. to Measure - zero is noisy, high - even on ground. Air flow rate too low.
08:58:10	A	0.62	U low signal (Near Air Flow) - 0.30 SLM
08:58:56	A	0.61	end Run ②

Engine Sec 10 to hr.

15 min.

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A532 Date: 5/6/97 Page: 2 / 6
 Campaign: _____ Operator(s): Wolfs
 Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)
 PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V
 Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
090620	Z	0.61/2	Start zero.
090828	A	0.64	Start descent @ 1000' FPM. Start profile ① from FL160
091306	A	0.60	⊕
13:29	A		Flow @ 10000' = 1.145 L/M.
091531	A	0.60	8000' descending @ 500 FPM
0921:40	A	0.65	5000' + descends. Flow = 1.53 ✓
0922:20	A	0.63	2000' + descends
092800	A		Start run ④ , End profile ① 900'
092818	A	0.64	Start run ④ start run ④
093717	A	0.65	Climb to 5000' End run ④ Start profile 2.1 from 1000'
094446	A	0.63	Start run ⑤, end profile.
095152	A	0.69	Flow = 1.69 End run ⑤ start profile ② to flight FL100
095650	Z		Start run ⑥, end profile @ 10000', Start zero
10:0620	-		Change to 190 counts
10:0343	Z		end 6 Minute zero. end 6.1
10:0348	A		Commence 6.2 Air Sample rate = 1.17
10:0937	A	0.67	≈ 0.85 ppbV on Brian's Pk.
10:10:12	A		climbing to 15000' end run 6.2 start profile 2.3
10:15:12	A	0.67	run ⑦ start at FL150 UNCERTAIN OF ZERO. (⑦ 5000')

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A533

Date: _____

Page: 3 / 6

Campaign: _____ Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
10:19:00	A	0.70	FL 150 - Air Sample at 0.7 SLM End of Run (7) Check + accelerate for Transit.
10:20:12	A		
10:22:54	A	0.80	17000 Sample rate = 0.81
10:26:27	A	0.70	end profile start Run (8) - at high speed. Lamp = 7.04 V FL 200, Sample = 0.71 SLM
10:31:10	Z	0.76	Start 10 min zero flow = 0.68
10:42:37	A	0.72	End Run (8), end zero
10:55:00	Z		Start 25 min zero.
11:01:07	Z	0.67	~ 6 1/2 mins into zero
11:07:05	Z	0.67/8	
11:13:43	A	0.68	- Period - 0.66 V zero - reason?
11:15:02	CABIN	0.68	Instrument STARTED SAMPLING CABIN AIR @ 0.56 SLM TO TEST INSTRUMENT WORKING.
11:19:48	zero (outside HT)	0.95	STARTED ZERO.
11:23:20	Z	0.70	
11:35:10	Z	0.64	0.5 PPM on briars PC - Variation on zero is 30 30 mV peak to trough - noise on line scale of 3-6 mins
11:58:17	A		END ZERO - AMBIENT SAMPLING at.
11:44:10	Z		START ZERO - checked filter filters in box making loose no. of air leaks.

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

Flight No: A532

Date: 5/1/97

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Campaign: TRANSIT 1120CES Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
11:55:40	Z	0.55	Tightened some fittings a little slightly
11:58:35	Z	0.54	- Poss air intake on wet chem bin leaked.
11:58:46	A	0.54	END ZERO- START AMBIENT
			MEASURE
12:06:35	A	0.58	- not showing on Brian's PC (below zero)
12:08:17	A	0.58	
12:10:38	A	0.59	
12:12:10	A	0.59	LAMP = 703, Flow = 0.71 SLM.
12:13:57	Z	0.58	START ZERO, FLOW = 0.64
			SPEED = 300 KNOTS. HEAT FL200
12:14:35	Z	0.59	} well below zero on Brian's PC
12:20:55	Z	0.57	
12:22:19	Z	0.56	
12:23:45	Z	0.57	
12:25:20	Z	0.56	
12:26:45	Z	0.55	
12:28:50	Z	0.55	
12:29:20	Z	0.54	
12:31:10	Z	0.53	
12:34:53	A	0.55	START MEASURE
12:36:25	A	0.55	
12:37:35	A	0.55	- 0.35 pptV on Laptop.
12:39:50	A	0.54	
12:43:00	A	0.56	
12:46:00	A	0.57	
12:47:39	A	0.58	
12:58:30	A	0.57	Flow 0.71, Lamp = 7.03
12:59:45	Z	0.57	Starting zero
13:07:30	Z	0.56	

Formaldehyde Instrument Log Sheet

 Flight No: A533 533

 Date: 5/6/97

 Page: 15 / 16

 Campaign: ACSOE - AZORES TRAILS Operator(s): _____

Air Sampling Rate: _____ Peristaltic Pump Speed: _____ (rpm)

PMT Sensitivity: _____ Calib Factor: _____ (V to ppt) _____ drs Bits = 1V

Approx Lag Time: _____ React Coil Temp: _____

Time (GMT)	Zero/Amb	Inst. Output (V)	Other Info/Remarks e.g. Altitude, lamp output, sampling rate changes etc.
13:04:55	Z	0.57	if zero is working it goes down V. slowly.
13:07:46	Z	0.54	} zero is <u>V. NOISY</u> / not proper zero.
13:10:00	Z	0.55	
13:11:10	Z	0.56	
13:14:11	Z	0.56	
13:18:04	Z	0.56	
13:24:41	Z	0.55	Run (9) @ fl 200 - steph calib
13:31:20	A	0.55	End zero. Start ambient sampling
13:49:00	A	0.58	Flow = 0.86 SLM
13:50:06	A	0.58	Fl 150 end profile (1) start Run 10 Flow = 0.91
13:55:00	A	0.57	
13:56:46	A	0.56	end Run 10 start Profile 3.2
14:00:00	A	0.58	Flow Flow = 1.07 SLM
14:01:35		0.57	End Profile 3.2 Start Run 11 Fl 100 Flow = 1.17
14:03:45	A	0.57/8	
14:06:27	A	0.59	- gets above zero on Brian's PC for fl 100
14:08:51	A	0.59	End Run 11, Start Profile 3.3 to 6000'
14:12:59	A		End Profile 3.3, Start Run 12 at fl 60
14:14:16	A	0.59	

Get Profile
 from Brian
 3:10

02Z -111 1724

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 05 APR 1997

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 263

04 APR '97 04:32 FROM MET 1TOPS BRACKNELL TO 489B

Original and drawn with Campbell's System, No. 0188. Station: MET 1TOPS BRACKNELL. Date: 05 APR 1997.

Printed on 28 x 44 cm (11 x 17 in) paper. No. 1250-2119

UUC MI CT 64

500-1000MB
500MB

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

T 24

GMAIN

5/4/97

VI 00Z SRI

4/4/97

4/4/97

DT 00Z FRI

CHART 15

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:41:36

PHE50 EGRR 0000Z

A533B.TXT

From 12Z 31/ 3/1997 to 12Z 5/ 4/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

A533 05-APR-97

P3 FL200-50'(134523-144717)

A533 05-APR-97

P1 FL160-900ft(90826-92800) + P2 1000'-FL200(93717-102627)

A533 fig

A533

A533 05-APR-97 R2 FL085 From 82330-82503 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:27

A533 05-APR-97 R2 FL085 From 82330-82503 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:27

A533 05-APR-97 R2 FL085 From 82330-82503 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:27

A533 05-APR-97 R2 FL085 From 82330-82503 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:27

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 737.357
 Standard dev 1.78361
 Max value 740.441
 Min value 734.691

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 272.924
 Standard dev 0.236399
 Max value 273.156
 Min value 272.061

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 271.295
 Standard dev 0.427490
 Max value 271.953
 Min value 270.616

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 55.6628
 Standard dev 0.928430
 Max value 57.6339
 Min value 53.4668

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 11.1468
 Standard dev 0.844887
 Max value 13.1873
 Min value 9.31313

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 0.213191
 Standard dev 1.532815e-02
 Max value 0.248000
 Min value 0.184000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 2601.40
 Standard dev 19.1982
 Max value 2630.13
 Min value 2568.23

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 55.3589
 Standard dev 5.862077e-03
 Max value 55.3686
 Min value 55.3487

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 94
 Mean -5.53357
 Standard dev 3.130574e-02
 Max value -5.47929
 Min value -5.58639

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 94
 Mean -13.0184
 Standard dev 0.755690
 Max value -11.8988
 Min value -14.7485

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 24.3692
 Standard dev 0.347412
 Max value 24.9626
 Min value 23.5071

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 94
 Mean -1.94333
 Standard dev 0.511130
 Max value -0.691391
 Min value -2.64047

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 27.6401
 Standard dev 0.220397
 Max value 28.1117
 Min value 27.1101

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 298.112

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 94
 Mean 103.658
 Standard dev 2.17663
 Max value 107.352
 Min value 101.050

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 288.076

A533 05-APR-97 R3 FL160 From 83649-85854 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:39

A533 05-APR-97 R3 FL160 From 83649-85854 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:39

A533 05-APR-97 R3 FL160 From 83649-85854 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:31

A533 05-APR-97 R3 FL160 From 83649-85854 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:31

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 548.207
 Standard dev 0.263001
 Max value 549.261
 Min value 547.531

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 258.376
 Standard dev 0.111055
 Max value 258.615
 Min value 257.971

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 248.668
 Standard dev 6.66747
 Max value 257.137
 Min value 231.216

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 62.8184
 Standard dev 2.31453
 Max value 69.0933
 Min value 57.6837

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 21.1982
 Standard dev 15.3716
 Max value 51.4538
 Min value 10.4053

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 0.299704
 Standard dev 0.141113
 Max value 0.592000
 Min value 7.999998e-03

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 4889.65
 Standard dev 3.59985
 Max value 4898.90
 Min value 4875.22

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 55.6955
 Standard dev 9.397659e-02
 Max value 55.8372
 Min value 55.5300

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean -7.29553
 Standard dev 0.492821
 Max value -6.43931
 Min value -8.16790

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean -13.8190
 Standard dev 1.20680
 Max value -11.6768
 Min value -16.6921

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 29.0868
 Standard dev 1.31891
 Max value 31.6714
 Min value 26.2524

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 0.548581
 Standard dev 0.583260
 Max value 2.48439
 Min value -0.546036

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 32.2353
 Standard dev 1.04305
 Max value 34.2121
 Min value 29.6865

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 295.412

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1326
 Mean 117.697
 Standard dev 1.95388
 Max value 121.516
 Min value 112.302

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 287.460

A533 05-APR-97 P1 FL160-900ft From 90826-92800 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:42

A533 05-APR-97 P1 FL160-900ft From 90826-92800 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:42

A533 05-APR-97 P1 FL160-900ft From 90826-92800 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:35

A533 05-APR-97 P1 FL160-900ft From 90826-92800 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:35

A533 05-APR-97 R4 1000' From 92818-93717 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:44

A533 05-APR-97 R4 1000' From 92818-93717 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:44

A533 05-APR-97 R4 1000' From 92818-93717 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:37

A533 05-APR-97 R4 1000' From 92818-93717 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:37

A533 05-APR-97 R4 1000' From 92818-93717 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:37

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 540
Mean 977.781
Standard dev 0.640348
Max value 980.338
Min value 975.879

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 540
Mean 281.571
Standard dev 5.408504e-02
Max value 281.697
Min value 281.393

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 540
Mean 282.839
Standard dev 0.188691
Max value 283.179
Min value 282.506

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 540
Mean 46.2774
Standard dev 1.18269
Max value 49.5574
Min value 43.3068

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 540
Mean 6.63933
Standard dev 13.2658
Max value 44.8228
Min value 1.38106

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 540
Mean 0.130178
Standard dev 1.454205e-02
Max value 0.184000
Min value 9.599999e-02

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 540
Mean 313.810
Standard dev 6.18957
Max value 326.933
Min value 288.462

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 540
Mean 55.8714
Standard dev 2.863221e-02
Max value 55.9220
Min value 55.8219

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 540
Mean -10.8114
Standard dev 0.179440
Max value -10.4990
Min value -11.1199

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 540
Mean -4.49686
Standard dev 0.506429
Max value -3.03989
Min value -6.12244

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 540
Mean 20.3977
Standard dev 0.811339
Max value 22.2689
Min value 17.5765

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 540
Mean -0.235238
Standard dev 0.327044
Max value 1.22458
Min value -1.05553

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 540
Mean 20.8930
Standard dev 0.827202
Max value 22.7801
Min value 18.0690

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 282.432

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 540
Mean 93.5981
Standard dev 0.832250
Max value 96.4381
Min value 91.1370

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 253.995

A533 05-APR-97 P2 1000'-FL200 From 93717-102627 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:49

A533 05-APR-97 P2 1000'-FL200 From 93717-102627 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:49

A533 05-APR-97 P2 1000'-FL200 From 93717-102627 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:45

A533 05-APR-97 P2 1000'-FL200 From 93717-102627 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:45

A533 05-APR-97 R5 FL050 From 94444-95152 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:51

A533 05-APR-97 R5 FL050 From 94444-95152 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:51

A533 05-APR-97 R5 FL050 From 94444-95152 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:47

A533 05-APR-97 R5 FL050 From 94444-95152 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:47

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 429
 Mean 842.145
 Standard dev 0.232544
 Max value 843.227
 Min value 841.237

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 429
 Mean 278.003
 Standard dev 0.281844
 Max value 278.425
 Min value 277.253

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 429
 Mean 277.364
 Standard dev 0.517352
 Max value 278.770
 Min value 276.646

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 429
 Mean 46.1710
 Standard dev 2.05366
 Max value 50.8360
 Min value 40.9600

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 429
 Mean 17.1162
 Standard dev 13.0118
 Max value 51.8643
 Min value 8.92847

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 429
 Mean 0.296205
 Standard dev 2.114028e-02
 Max value 0.368000
 Min value 0.240000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 429
 Mean 1532.94
 Standard dev 2.24829
 Max value 1541.72
 Min value 1522.49

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 429
 Mean 55.6665
 Standard dev 2.908152e-02
 Max value 55.7152
 Min value 55.6163

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 429
 Mean -11.9169
 Standard dev 0.153690
 Max value -11.6508
 Min value -12.1816

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 429
 Mean -7.87126
 Standard dev 0.442960
 Max value -6.52467
 Min value -9.10201

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 429
 Mean 20.1452
 Standard dev 0.435937
 Max value 21.1613
 Min value 19.1954

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 429
 Mean 0.148370
 Standard dev 0.429728
 Max value 0.886299
 Min value -1.15054

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 429
 Mean 21.6314
 Standard dev 0.502047
 Max value 22.9788
 Min value 20.6895

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 291.342

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 429
 Mean 99.4314
 Standard dev 1.03722
 Max value 101.524
 Min value 95.1982

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 251.753

A533 05-APR-97 R6 FL100 From 95650-101012 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:53

A533 05-APR-97 R6 FL100 From 95650-101012 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:53

A533 05-APR-97 R6 FL100 From 95650-101012 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:49

A533 05-APR-97 R6 FL100 From 95650-101012 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:50

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 803
 Mean 696.211
 Standard dev 0.639922
 Max value 697.455
 Min value 694.410

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 803
 Mean 270.365
 Standard dev 0.172819
 Max value 270.943
 Min value 270.106

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 803
 Mean 269.258
 Standard dev 0.295718
 Max value 270.065
 Min value 268.387

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 803
 Mean 46.1757
 Standard dev 1.23656
 Max value 50.1595
 Min value 43.3801

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 803
 Mean 13.7694
 Standard dev 10.3594
 Max value 51.3845
 Min value 9.09481

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 803
 Mean 0.238705
 Standard dev 0.114301
 Max value 0.392000
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 803
 Mean 3054.78
 Standard dev 7.21809
 Max value 3075.12
 Min value 3040.75

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 803
 Mean 55.4344
 Standard dev 7.208925e-02
 Max value 55.5507
 Min value 55.3073

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 803
 Mean -13.0992
 Standard dev 0.318590
 Max value -12.5556
 Min value -13.6557

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 803
 Mean -7.61142
 Standard dev 0.647851
 Max value -6.22020
 Min value -9.62280

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 803
 Mean 21.2164
 Standard dev 0.722136
 Max value 22.8086
 Min value 19.0989

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 803
 Mean 0.293788
 Standard dev 0.449129
 Max value 1.19840
 Min value -1.43594

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 803
 Mean 22.5488
 Standard dev 0.749501
 Max value 24.0211
 Min value 20.2061

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 289.736

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 803
 Mean 110.903
 Standard dev 2.62230
 Max value 115.223
 Min value 106.340

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 248.732

A533 05-APR-97 R7 FL150 From 101513-102012 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:54

A533 05-APR-97 R7 FL150 From 101513-102012 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:54

A533 05-APR-97 R7 FL150 From 101513-102012 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:50

A533 05--APR--97 R7 FL150 From 101513-102012 Plotted 6--Jun--1997 16:50

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 300
 Mean 571.289
 Standard dev 0.539647
 Max value 572.317
 Min value 569.726

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 300
 Mean 260.633
 Standard dev 0.536143
 Max value 261.410
 Min value 259.812

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 300
 Mean 259.059
 Standard dev 0.951699
 Max value 260.573
 Min value 257.672

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 300
 Mean 47.1085
 Standard dev 0.831247
 Max value 49.7716
 Min value 45.3332

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 300
 Mean 20.0913
 Standard dev 10.6469
 Max value 53.1770
 Min value 11.4120

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 300
 Mean 0.395173
 Standard dev 7.626013e-02
 Max value 0.536000
 Min value 0.248000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 300
 Mean 4578.94
 Standard dev 7.14531
 Max value 4599.66
 Min value 4565.35

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 300
 Mean 55.1694
 Standard dev 2.557718e-02
 Max value 55.2125
 Min value 55.1249

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 300
 Mean -14.2815
 Standard dev 0.129101
 Max value -14.0626
 Min value -14.5050

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 300
 Mean 0.962038
 Standard dev 0.617055
 Max value 2.32682
 Min value -0.521133

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 300
 Mean 23.6065
 Standard dev 0.705764
 Max value 25.4005
 Min value 22.3744

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 300
 Mean -0.105525
 Standard dev 0.836489
 Max value 1.13803
 Min value -2.64005

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 300
 Mean 23.6340
 Standard dev 0.710379
 Max value 25.4187
 Min value 22.4239

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 267.666

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 300
 Mean 122.347
 Standard dev 2.70352
 Max value 124.499
 Min value 110.298

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 250.918

A533 05-APR-97 R8 FL200 From 102627-104337 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:57

A533 05-APR-97 R8 FL200 From 102627-104337 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:57

A533 05-APR-97 R8 FL200 From 102627-104337 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:54

A533 05-APR-97 R8 FL200 From 102627-104337 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:54

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 465.073
 Standard dev 0.339246
 Max value 466.307
 Min value 464.318

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 253.062
 Standard dev 0.231955
 Max value 253.593
 Min value 252.583

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 233.937
 Standard dev 3.77224
 Max value 249.461
 Min value 229.400

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 58.2649
 Standard dev 6.55644
 Max value 69.3600
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 18.7331
 Standard dev 9.23335
 Max value 53.5780
 Min value 15.0879

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 0.137451
 Standard dev 8.244839e-02
 Max value 0.352000
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 6104.65
 Standard dev 5.30254
 Max value 6116.47
 Min value 6085.37

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 54.4238
 Standard dev 0.348104
 Max value 54.9983
 Min value 53.8117

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1031
 Mean -15.3536
 Standard dev 0.239467
 Max value -14.9698
 Min value -15.7646

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1031
 Mean -2.64180
 Standard dev 0.854647
 Max value 0.135788
 Min value -4.33119

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 32.1455
 Standard dev 2.15824
 Max value 36.3511
 Min value 28.6473

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 0.827874
 Standard dev 0.778017
 Max value 3.16579
 Min value -3.10506

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 32.2639
 Standard dev 2.17701
 Max value 36.4995
 Min value 28.8188

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 274.698

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1031
 Mean 150.179
 Standard dev 9.91324
 Max value 157.243
 Min value 112.725

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 201.343

A533 05-APR-97 R9 FL200 From 132441-134433 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:59

A533 05-APR-97 R9 FL200 From 132441-134433 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 08:59

A533 05-APR-97 R9 FL200 From 132441-134433 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:57

A533 05-APR-97 R9 FL200 From 132441-134433 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 16:57

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 466.696
 Standard dev 8.303984e-02
 Max value 466.965
 Min value 466.429

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 250.363
 Standard dev 0.274100
 Max value 250.868
 Min value 250.014

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 240.780
 Standard dev 1.52444
 Max value 243.649
 Min value 238.057

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 61.2850
 Standard dev 6.72478
 Max value 69.5501
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 20.4613
 Standard dev 8.75037
 Max value 51.1255
 Min value 16.7380

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 0.372842
 Standard dev 5.305034e-02
 Max value 0.552000
 Min value 0.216000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 6079.30
 Standard dev 1.29484
 Max value 6083.46
 Min value 6075.11

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 40.6900
 Standard dev 0.472726
 Max value 41.5115
 Min value 39.8985

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean -22.7808
 Standard dev 0.175753
 Max value -22.5253
 Min value -23.1829

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 1.87937
 Standard dev 1.39748
 Max value 4.39805
 Min value -0.865295

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean -7.39838
 Standard dev 0.926913
 Max value -5.66239
 Min value -9.51241

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 0.789812
 Standard dev 0.279032
 Max value 1.60181
 Min value -0.208572

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 7.77364
 Standard dev 0.805546
 Max value 9.66836
 Min value 6.20100

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 104.253

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1193
 Mean 158.990
 Standard dev 0.500406
 Max value 160.159
 Min value 156.500

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 197.299

A533 05-APR-97 P3 FL200-50' From 134523-144717 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:06

A533 05-APR-97 P3 FL200-50' From 134523-144717 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:06

A533 05-APR-97 P3 FL200-50' From 134523-144717 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:04

A533 05-APR-97 P3 FL200-50' From 134523-144717 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:04

A533 05-APR-97 R10 FL150 From 135006-135646 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:07

A533 05-APR-97 R10 FL150 From 135006 - 135646 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:07

A533 05-APR-97 R10 FL150 From 135006-135646 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:05

A533 05-APR-97 R10 FL150 From 135006 - 135646 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:05

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 401
 Mean 572.557
 Standard dev 0.633263
 Max value 573.892
 Min value 571.017

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 401
 Mean 260.688
 Standard dev 0.115036
 Max value 260.945
 Min value 260.471

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 401
 Mean 256.209
 Standard dev 0.343592
 Max value 256.869
 Min value 255.394

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 401
 Mean 50.0294
 Standard dev 0.939291
 Max value 52.3580
 Min value 47.6808

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 401
 Mean 19.3511
 Standard dev 10.4623
 Max value 52.3119
 Min value 15.3616

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 401
 Mean 0.940309
 Standard dev 0.124116
 Max value 1.10400
 Min value 0.680000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 401
 Mean 4562.18
 Standard dev 8.36975
 Max value 4582.54
 Min value 4544.54

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 401
 Mean 39.4344
 Standard dev 9.737230e-02
 Max value 39.6022
 Min value 39.2666

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 401
 Mean -23.6592
 Standard dev 9.350554e-02
 Max value -23.4936
 Min value -23.8186

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 401
 Mean 1.17810
 Standard dev 0.504182
 Max value 2.09000
 Min value -0.113708

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 401
 Mean -3.86939
 Standard dev 0.687722
 Max value -2.55850
 Min value -5.41476

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 401
 Mean 0.716103
 Standard dev 0.971526
 Max value 2.65372
 Min value -0.572060

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 401
 Mean 4.09518
 Standard dev 0.561911
 Max value 5.42727
 Min value 2.86638

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 106.934

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 401
 Mean 115.007
 Standard dev 1.37772
 Max value 119.655
 Min value 112.426

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 216.904

A533 05-APR-97 R11 FL100 From 140135-140851 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:08

A533 05-APR-97 R11 FL100 From 140135-140851 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:08

A533 05-APR-97 R11 FL100 From 140135-140851 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:06

A533 05-APR-97 R11 FL100 From 140135-140851 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:06

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 437
 Mean 697.545
 Standard dev 0.441022
 Max value 699.063
 Min value 696.586

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 437
 Mean 271.713
 Standard dev 6.829476e-02
 Max value 271.891
 Min value 271.580

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 437
 Mean 268.002
 Standard dev 0.214470
 Max value 268.354
 Min value 267.479

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 437
 Mean 47.6915
 Standard dev 1.19394
 Max value 51.1883
 Min value 44.2589

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 437
 Mean 20.2797
 Standard dev 9.36895
 Max value 52.1198
 Min value 16.7211

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 437
 Mean 1.33000
 Standard dev 8.163451e-02
 Max value 1.49600
 Min value 1.08000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 437
 Mean 3039.74
 Standard dev 4.96504
 Max value 3050.55
 Min value 3022.66

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 437
 Mean 38.8767
 Standard dev 9.397245e-02
 Max value 39.0386
 Min value 38.7129

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 437
 Mean -24.2341
 Standard dev 0.102081
 Max value -24.0576
 Min value -24.4055

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 437
 Mean 1.48490
 Standard dev 0.510290
 Max value 2.56222
 Min value 0.561409

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 437
 Mean -3.03286
 Standard dev 0.421684
 Max value -1.87206
 Min value -4.04827

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 437
 Mean 0.928916
 Standard dev 0.806282
 Max value 2.52090
 Min value -7.353210e-02

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 437
 Mean 3.39173
 Standard dev 0.580760
 Max value 4.69400
 Min value 2.07470

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 116.087

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 437
 Mean 107.130
 Standard dev 0.904814
 Max value 109.653
 Min value 105.699

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 219.844

A533 05-APR-97 R12 6000' From 141259 - 143231 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:10

A533 05-APR-97 R12 6000' From 141259-143231 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:10

A533 05-APR-97 R12 600' From 141259-143231 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:09

A533 05-APR-97 R12 6000' From 141259-143231 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:09

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 816.533
 Standard dev 0.718121
 Max value 819.999
 Min value 813.558

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 282.270
 Standard dev 0.186310
 Max value 282.824
 Min value 281.874

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 271.351
 Standard dev 0.326683
 Max value 272.164
 Min value 270.324

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 50.1677
 Standard dev 1.00961
 Max value 53.3890
 Min value 47.3646

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 22.9146
 Standard dev 12.8760
 Max value 54.4498
 Min value 11.7058

PEROXIDE (PPB)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 1.26373
 Standard dev 0.473448
 Max value 1.68800
 Min value 3.999999e-02

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 1783.69
 Standard dev 7.11492
 Max value 1813.22
 Min value 1749.39

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 38.1079
 Standard dev 0.234417
 Max value 38.5215
 Min value 37.7157

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean -25.0798
 Standard dev 0.288240
 Max value -24.5886
 Min value -25.5775

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 5.243809e-02
 Standard dev 0.931075
 Max value 2.85435
 Min value -1.19938

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean -8.26158
 Standard dev 0.583200
 Max value -6.99300
 Min value -9.63699

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 0.600879
 Standard dev 0.523554
 Max value 2.64445
 Min value -0.287956

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 8.31603
 Standard dev 0.553352
 Max value 9.64954
 Min value 7.29106

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 90.3637

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1173
 Mean 101.380
 Standard dev 1.40838
 Max value 105.147
 Min value 97.5793

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 223.981

A533 05-APR-97 R13 3500' From 143519-144055 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:11

A533 05-APR-97 R13 3500' From 143519-144055 Plotted 19-Jun-1997 09:11

A533 05-APR-97 R13 3500' From 143519-144055 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:10

A533 05-APR-97 R13 3500' From 143519-144055 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:10

A533 05-APR-97 R13 3500' From 143519-144055 Plotted 6-Jun-1997 17:10

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 337
Mean 893.594
Standard dev 0.426083
Max value 895.595
Min value 892.192

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 337
Mean 285.750
Standard dev 0.627250
Max value 286.585
Min value 282.993

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 337
Mean 272.558
Standard dev 1.19674
Max value 276.646
Min value 271.240

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 337
Mean 69.1414
Standard dev 1.41925
Max value 72.8405
Min value 65.3471

JNO2 TOTAL (E-3/S)

No of obs 337
Mean 20.6947
Standard dev 16.9695
Max value 53.2552
Min value 11.3002

PEROXIDE (PPB)

No of obs 337
Mean 1.51240
Standard dev 3.348388e-02
Max value 1.68800
Min value 1.40800

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 337
Mean 1095.70
Standard dev 4.14866
Max value 1109.18
Min value 1075.92

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 337
Mean 37.4210
Standard dev 8.644789e-02
Max value 37.5697
Min value 37.2714

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 337
Mean -25.5220
Standard dev 9.614103e-03
Max value -25.5053
Min value -25.5391

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 337
Mean -2.64451
Standard dev 0.849605
Max value -1.26584
Min value -7.23473

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 337
Mean -8.40238
Standard dev 0.939100
Max value -2.83354
Min value -9.72157

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 337
Mean 0.873203
Standard dev 0.633829
Max value 2.03085
Min value -1.97231

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 337
Mean 8.88181
Standard dev 0.553799
Max value 9.85980
Min value 5.51236

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 72.5294

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 337
Mean 97.2508
Standard dev 1.57914
Max value 100.766
Min value 91.4709

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 174.842

Instrument Log Sheet: Remuda

Flight No: 533

Date: 5/4/92

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Campaign: AC302/ALONE
TRANSIT

Operator(s): BJS

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
			Zero	Mode A = 620 B = 620
06:58			Cal	Mod 1.22 HU B 1.21 30 Range DES 1) 240 A & B 2) 245 A & B 1.4 L/min Pseudo Run @ 40 sec
07:08:35				Level Change
07:53:10			Zero On	Level Change
08:13	4000'		Zero On	End of Plot
08:14	4000'	Run 1	Zero Off	
8:16:40				Range to Zero Point → 160 sec log, H ₂ O 190 sec log, O ₂
08:19:02		End Run		
	↑			Cloud ≈ 6000'
08:23:24	8500'	Run 2		
08:24:16			Zero On	Cloudy bc get out of cloud
08:25:03		End 2		
08:27			Zero Off	Zero A & B .04
08:36:42	16000'	Start Run 3		
08:39			Zero On	
08:42			Zero Off	
08:46	16000'			1.4 L/min direct
08:55:54	16000'	End 3		Partial descent to 1500'
	↓	St P		
09:08:25		St P 1		from 16000 @ 1000'/min
09:15:31	8500'			500'/min Descent
09:22	4500'	↓		

Instrument Log Sheet: 1102

Flight No: S33

Date: 5/4/97

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Campaign: ASPE (A2012)
TILW317

Operator(s): RSSB

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
0926	2000'	ER1	M	1.4 L/min Air Flow
0928	1000'	SP4		
09		ER4+		In Cloud
0937 ¹⁷	4	SP2.1		Cloudy @ 500' / min
093717	5000'			
094444	5100'	SP5		
095151		ER6		
	10000' ↑	SP2.2		Cloudy @ 1000' / min In & out cloud
95620				Near End Taps
95649		End P27		
+ ↘	10000	SP6.1		Zeroing on Heats / H ₂ / W ₂
095700		Zero on		
100000		Zero off		
100551		ER6.1		
		SP6.2		Dater run
101013		ER6.2		
101013		SP2.3	To 15000'	1000' / min
10512		ER2.3		
10512	15000'	SP2.4		
102012		ER7		
	↑	SP2.4		Accelerated up to 20000' & Turned to Altimeter @ 20000' Speed.
10:21 40	16500			1.35 Flow Rate
	17500			1.28
	19000			1.2
102626	20000'	ER2.4		-15°C Wind 275°
1032	20000		Zero on	@ 66 L/min
1035	20000		Zero off	

Instrument Log Sheet: H₂O

Flight No: 533

Date: 5/4/97

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Campaign: ACESE / 120000 TRANSIT Operator(s): SR

Time (GMT)	Altitude	Run	Zero / Cal	Comments
122500	20000'		Zero on	ASB @ 04 Vals.
122900	20000'		Zero off	1.15 L/min flow
<p>(Get pump and flow) (Anderson Key / K. Law)</p>				<p>Continuing Correlation 1-1 H₂O mass / H₂O medallion from descent 10:35 - 1220 also regular correlation with O₃ of water vapor</p>
130120			Zero on	Zero very constant
130420			Zero off	
132441	20000'	SR9		Wait open system Escapes with finite speed of airplane
134624	20000'	ER9		
134524	↓	SP3.1		Probing in stars for 50'
135006	15000'	EP3.1		
135006		SR10		Flow rate 1.4 L/min
135646	15000'	ER10		
135646	↓	SP3.2		(1.2 ppb H ₂ O @ 15000')
140135		EP3.2		
140135	10000'	SR11		180 knots indicated speed
140850	10000'	ER11		
140850	↓	SP3.3		Flow Rate 1.4 L/min
141255		EP3.3		
141255	6000'	SR12		
		ER12		
141520			Zero on	B A 0.04 10.03
1421.20			Zero off	
143231	6000'	ER12		
143231	↓	SP3.4		Descent to 3500'
1435		EP3.4		

The first part of the document discusses the importance of maintaining accurate records of all transactions. It emphasizes that every entry should be supported by a valid receipt or invoice. This ensures transparency and allows for easy auditing of the accounts.

In the second section, the author details the various methods used to collect and analyze data. This includes both primary and secondary research techniques. The primary research involves direct observation and interviews, while secondary research involves reviewing existing literature and reports.

The third section focuses on the statistical analysis of the collected data. It describes the use of various statistical tests to determine the significance of the findings. The results indicate a strong correlation between the variables being studied, which supports the initial hypothesis.

Finally, the document concludes with a summary of the key findings and their implications. It suggests that the results have important implications for the field of study and provides recommendations for further research. The author also acknowledges the limitations of the study and offers suggestions for how these can be addressed in future work.

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument "the fluorescence water vapour sensor".

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm^3) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3][H_2O]) / (k_5 [M](j_6 + k_7 + [OH]k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + hv \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + hv \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4, j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}, NO_{y2}) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in volts. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).
- **Bags/CO analysis:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office). Analysis was carried out at ITE Edinburgh by Neil Cape. Plots of CO (ppb) with altitude (pressure height in metres) are included. Contamination has been noted in some of the bag samples, for further advice contact ITE Edinburgh.

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